

THE PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO
THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD - N·C·S-. PART IV. THE
ACTION OF AQUEOUS SILVER NITRATE ON
PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE.

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Phenylthiocarbamide interferes with the estimation of thiocyanic acid by Volhard's method. The objects of the present investigation are to see how silver nitrate interacts with phenylthiocarbamide in acid solution, and to determine the conditions in which Volhard's method can be used to estimate thiocyanic acid in the presence of thiocarbamide.

By the interaction of aqueous solutions of phenylthiocarbamide and silver nitrate, a white precipitate is obtained which is stable in presence of dilute nitric acid. Analytical results indicate the formation of several complexes of these two compounds which vary in composition with the proportion of the reagents used. The complex having the largest proportion of silver nitrate is formed when an aqueous solution of phenylthiocarbamide is treated with moderate excess of silver nitrate. It is certainly not a silver derivative but appears to be a complex (1:1), although it usually takes up 10-12% extra silver nitrate, a fact which indicates the existence of still higher complexes. By using less silver nitrate lower complexes are obtained which appear to be of less interest. The monomolecular complex reacts with potassium thiocyanate changing to phenylthiocarbamide-silver thiocyanate. The latter is also formed directly by the interaction of phenylthiocarbamide and silver thiocyanate or of phenylthiocarbamide, silver nitrate and potassium thiocyanate.

These complex formations may be represented as follows :

Volhard's method, using excess of silver nitrate and titrating back with standard potassium thiocyanate, can be used to estimate thiocyanic acid provided that the phenylthiocarbamide present is less in molecular propor-

tions than the thiocyanic acid. Ten molecular proportions of phenylthiocarbamide correspond to eleven of silver nitrate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Expt. 1. Action of Aqueous Silver Nitrate on Phenylthiocarbamide in presence of a Variable quantity of Nitric Acid.—The variable amount of nitric acid was added to 50 c.c. of *N*/50-phenylthiocarbamide solution in 4% alcohol (the solubility in water alone is very low) followed by 15 c.c. of *N*/10- silver nitrate drop by drop with shaking; after a minute or so it was filtered, washed with dilute nitric acid (2%) and the filtrate titrated back with *N*/10-potassium thiocyanate, using 5 c.c. of 5% ferric alum as indicator. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I.

2 <i>N</i> -HNO ₃ (c.c.)	...	0.3	0.5	1	2	3	4	6	8	10	20
AgNO ₃ used up (c.c.)	...	11	11.1	11.1	11	11	11	11	11	10.9	9.5

Below 2 c.c. and above 8 c.c. the interaction was more or less incomplete but within this range uniform results were obtained and we have, therefore, in all our experiments used 5 c.c. of 2*N*-nitric acid for every 100 c.c. of solution.

It will be noted that 50 c.c. of phenylthiocarbamide solution took up 11 c.c. of silver nitrate, whereas one equivalent is 10 c.c. Discussion of this phenomenon would be out of place but it may be mentioned that we have found that

- (i) the excess of silver nitrate can be removed by suspending the precipitate in dilute nitric acid;
- (ii) it is not a case of adsorption;
- (iii) as little as 5 c.c. of silver nitrate remove all the phenylthiocarbamide from solution with the formation of a different complex;
- (iv) in aqueous solutions the excess of nitrate taken up is never more than 10-12% of the equivalent;
- (v) in alcoholic solutions complexes richer in silver nitrate are formed.

Expt. 2. Examination of the Phenylthiocarbamide—Silver nitrate Complex obtained in the Above Experiment.—Heated on a nickel foil it exploded evolving voluminous yellow fumes. Decomposition occurred at 132-34°. Hot water, ammonia and alkalis decomposed it readily but it

could be recrystallised with slight decomposition from dilute nitric acid. It interacted slowly with potassium thiocyanate solution (*vide infra*).

1.61 G. of the substance, suspended in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) and treated with hydrogen sulphide, gave silver sulphide (Ag, 33.08 per cent). The alcoholic solution gave a copious precipitate with nitron acetate showing that the complex contained nitrate, while on evaporation to dryness it deposited unmistakable crystals of phenylthiocarbamide showing that this molecule had not undergone any change.

Phenylthiocarbamide solution (50 c.c. of *N*/50) yielded 0.3352 g. of the complex containing Ag, 33.52; S, 10.08%. $\text{PhNHCSNH}_2 \cdot \text{AgNO}_3$ requires 0.3328 g. of the complex and Ag, 33.32; S, 9.936 per cent.

Expt. 3. Action of Potassium Thiocyanate Solution on the above Complex.—The precipitate formed above was suspended in 50 c.c. of dilute nitric acid and treated with 15 c.c. of *N*/10-potassium thiocyanate. By filtering and titrating back, the amount of thiocyanate used up by interaction with the silver complex was determined.

TABLE II.

Time (hour)	...	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	6	24
<i>N</i> /10-KSCN used (c.c.)	...	5	6	9	9

The same product was slowly obtained by the interaction of freshly precipitated silver thiocyanate with a solution of phenylthiocarbamide. It was obtained more readily as follows.

Expt. 4. Action of Silver Nitrate on a Mixture of Phenylthiocarbamide and Potassium Thiocyanate.—When *N*/10- solutions were mixed, the silver nitrate being added last, a precipitate was formed; the filtrate from this contained no silver and no phenylthiocarbamide; it contained only a trace of thiocyanate.

In fact it appears that the solutions of three substances, thiocarbamide, silver nitrate and thiocyanate, mixed in any order, always give the same result.

Expt. 5. Examination of the Phenylthiocarbamide-Silver Thiocyanate Complex.—Heated on a nickel foil it fused without evolving fumes. It was insoluble in alcohol or water. Hot water and strong nitric acid decomposed it, whilst cold dilute acid had only a very slight action.

From 50 c.c. of the thiocarbamide solution the yield of the complex was 0.3160 g. containing Ag, 34.1; S, 20.13 per cent. $\text{PhNHCSNH}_2 \cdot \text{AgSCN}$ requires 0.3180 g. of the complex and Ag, 33.96; S, 20.01 per cent,

These results clearly explain the fact, repeatedly corroborated by titrations, that thiocyanate can be estimated by Volhard's method in the presence of phenylthiocarbamide *so long as the latter is less than equivalent to the former*, because it is precipitated with the former; whereas if the thiocarbamide is in excess, the thiocyanate cannot be estimated because thiocarbamide also interacts with silver nitrate.

It is remarkable that under conditions precisely analogous to those employed in the present investigation copper sulphate, besides forming various complexes, oxidises part of the phenylthiocarbamide to a base which on analysis and from its nitroso derivative proved to be Hector's danilino-*o*-diazothiol (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1176). No evidence of any such change has been found when using silver nitrate.

S U M M A R Y.

1. Silver nitrate unites with phenylthiocarbamide in acid solution to form several complexes and the compound $\text{PhNHCSNH}_2 \cdot \text{AgNO}_3$ is formed in the presence of excess of aqueous silver nitrate, 10-12% extra silver nitrate being used up in the latter case.

2. Potassium thiocyanate interacts with the above compound and changes it to phenylthiocarbamide-silverthiocyanate.

3. Thiocyanate can be conveniently estimated with a fair degree of accuracy in the presence of phenylthiocarbamide by Volhard's method under the conditions described but only if the phenylthiocarbamide is present in a quantity less than one equivalent to the thiocyanate.

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